

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE 13-WEEK MODERN ARNIS TRAINING EXPOSURE ON PUSH-UP PERFORMANCE

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The Effectiveness of the 13-week Modern Arnis Training Exposure on Push-up Performance

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Abstract

Push-up performance is an important predictor of upper-body muscle strength and endurance. However, pre-test results showed that a sizable proportion of Grade 11 students at Xavier University - Senior High School fared badly, raising concerns about their muscle fitness and overall health. The purpose of this study was to look into how a 13-week Modern Arnis training program affected push-up performance. The study comprised 1,000 Grade 11 students who underwent Modern Arnis instruction as part of their curriculum, and it employed a pre-experimental one-group pretest-posttest action research technique. Push-up repetitions were counted before and after fitness assessments to track development. The findings demonstrated a significant improvement in push-up ability after training, indicating the potential of martial arts-based therapies to improve physical fitness. However, limitations such as self-reporting accuracy and improper execution of movements may affect assessment reliability. Future studies should explore strategies to enhance data validity and investigate additional benefits of Modern Arnis training on overall health and fitness.

Keywords: *effectiveness, training exposure, performance, arnis*

Introduction

Push-up performance is an indicator of one's arm muscular strength and endurance. It is determined by the number repetitions a person can execute until failure (Revised Physical Fitness Test Manual, 2019). However, based on the push-up performance of the grade 11 physical education & health (PEH) 102 students during their mandatory pre-physical fitness test, it was observed that there is a significant number of poor performances among the students. This alarmed the researchers for poor performances in a push-up test, indicate poor muscular strength and endurance (Artanayasa et al., 2023; Revised Physical Fitness Test Manual, 2019; Rozenek et al., 2022), indicating poor health (Dhar & Purwar, 2023; Goud et al., 2023). With this, the researchers are committed to exploring the topic and devising a method or intervention to improve such performance.

Push-up performance has been explored before in the same institution by Endab et al. (2024). The study was about improving the push-up performance of five participants using the alternative exercise called modified push-up or the kneeling push-up. Based on the study, the push-up performance was really improved by at least 200% (Endab et al., 2024). This provides information or evidence that push-up performance can really improve by a program.

Poor arm strength and endurance are not merely indicators of limited physical capabilities but can also signify broader health issues. Research has shown that diminished muscle strength and endurance, particularly in the arms, are associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases and other chronic conditions. A comparative study by Goud et al. (2023) found that individuals with greater arm muscle strength exhibit better overall health and are less likely to suffer from chronic illnesses such as hypertension, diabetes, and obesity. This highlights the importance of maintaining muscle strength through regular physical activity as a preventative health strategy (Goud et al., 2023).

In this study, the teacher-researchers is committed to investigating the effects of the 13-week Modern Arnis training exposure to the push-up performance of the grade 11 students at Xavier University – Senior High School. There is an on-going methodological gap as the previously conducted study utilized a quasi-experimental design with an intervention of modified push-up (Endab et al., 2024). In this study, the intervention is the Modern Arnis training and the design will be one-group pretest-posttest action research design.

The researchers of this study chose the topic push-up performance because of two reasons: 1) push-up performance as a crucial component of one's fitness and 2) the push-up performance is one of the most convenient tests that can be administered even without an equipment. The researchers chose the grade 11 students as the participants of this study for two reasons; 1) the grade 11 curriculum is a Modern Arnis training that allows students to train their arms and 2) only the grade 11 students completed the pre-test, training, and post-test phases.

This research paper is dedicated to enhancing the push-up performance of the Grade 11 students through Modern Arnis training. The focus is exclusively on these students, incorporating a detailed examination of their successfully executed push-up. To this end, the study will involve 1,000 Grade 11 students engaging in Modern Arnis activities. The data to be collected are the number of push-up repetitions only during the students' pre-and post-physical fitness test.

This study intentionally excludes Grade 12 learners to maintain a focused exploration of the prescribed group. Moreover, the study will not address the reasons behind students' poor performance on the push-up test. This strategic exclusion ensures a concentrated investigation into how the Modern Arnis training will enhance the push-up performance of students within this academic context at

Xavier Ateneo Senior High School.

Research Questions

The researchers devised questions that could guide the direction of the current investigation on the effectiveness of the 13-week Modern Arnis training to the push-up performance of the grade 11 students. These are the guide questions of the researchers:

1. What is the push-up performance of the participants before and after Modern Arnis training?
2. Is there a significant difference between the participants' push-up performance before and after Modern Arnis training?

Literature Review

Push-up Performance

Push-up performance is a comprehensive indicator of upper body strength and endurance, valuable across various sports and activities. Research has identified several methods to enhance this performance effectively. For instance, a study by Subrata et al. (2022) found that varying the tempo of push-up exercises, specifically slowing down the eccentric phase, significantly improved push-up performance in medical students. This suggests that manipulating exercise tempo can enhance muscular endurance and strength (Subrata et al., 2022). Additionally, Nazilah et al. (2023) demonstrated that regular push-up training could significantly increase the speed of breaststroke swimming, indicating the transfer of push-up benefits to other physical performances (Nazilah et al., 2023).

Conducting a push-up test effectively measures upper body strength and endurance, offering insights into an individual's physical fitness level. The test typically begins with the participant in a prone position on a flat surface, with hands placed shoulder-width apart and the body forming a straight line from head to heels. Participants lower their bodies by bending at the elbows until the chest or chin nearly touches the ground, then push back up to the starting position, counting each complete push-up. This continues until the participant can no longer maintain proper form or complete a full push-up (Revised Physical Fitness Test Manual, 2019).

Incorporating unstable surfaces in push-up training is another method shown to enhance muscular activation and overall push-up efficacy. Marquina Nieto et al. (2022) analyzed push-ups performed on different unstable surfaces and found increased muscle activation and performance, particularly when using rings or suspension training systems like TRX. This type of training promotes greater neuromuscular engagement, improving strength and endurance over time (Marquina Nieto et al., 2022). Rozenek et al. (2022) further investigated the effects of varying cadences on push-up performance and found that self-selected or faster cadences could maximize performance, suggesting a personalized approach to push-up training can be beneficial (Rozenek et al., 2022).

Progressive overload, through increasing repetition numbers or adding weight, is crucial for advancing push-up performance. Amara et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of progressively loading push-ups to improve overall upper body strength in swimmers, which was directly correlated with better swimming performance. Their study underscores the critical role of structured, progressive resistance training in developing strength and power relevant to sports performance (Amara et al., 2021). Furthermore, Abu Talip et al. (2021) compared push-ups and bench press exercises, finding that both significantly improved muscular strength and endurance in sedentary individuals, demonstrating that push-ups can be an effective alternative to traditional weightlifting for enhancing muscle performance (Abu Talip et al., 2021).

Studies emphasize the significance of push-up performance as an indicator of health, namely in terms of physical strength and endurance, which are crucial for general well-being. The 2020 recommendations from the World Health Organization emphasize the need of engaging in muscle-strengthening exercises, such as push-ups, to preserve health in individuals of all age categories. Frequent participation in such activities is associated with a reduced likelihood of developing metabolic syndrome, obesity, cardiovascular illnesses, and other health problems (Bull et al., 2020).

Modern Arnis and Arm Strength and Endurance

Modern Arnis training, a martial art originating from the Philippines, is renowned for its use of sticks, knives, and open-hand methods. It provides a distinctive method for enhancing arm strength and endurance. This martial art prioritizes both accuracy and quickness, while also demanding continuous muscle activation, therefore serving as a great method for enhancing upper body strength. Lipardo et al. (2022) conducted a research which found that Arnis training has a notable impact on balance control, suggesting that it has the potential to boost muscular coordination and strength. This is especially important since the dynamic motions required in Arnis need ongoing arm movement and resistance, resulting in the gradual development of muscular endurance (Lipardo et al., 2022).

In addition, the practices of striking and blocking that are key to Modern Arnis training give a cardiovascular workout that builds overall endurance, especially in the upper limbs. This is because these practices are repeated over and over again. When it comes to properly employing Arnis in self-defense scenarios that may need prolonged physical engagement, it is vital to combine strength training with endurance training. Participating in martial arts training, such as Arnis, has been shown to result in increased levels of VO₂ max and muscle endurance, according to research. According to Azeez and Majeed (2022), this indicates that regular practice has the potential to significantly improve both arm strength and endurance.

In summary, this chapter has analyzed a number of literature and studies on push-up performance and Modern Arnis training. It

emphasizes the importance of push-ups in evaluating and enhancing arm strength and endurance, which has a significant influence on both athletic performance and general well-being.

Methodology

Research Design

This study will utilize a one-group pretest-posttest action research design. Action research is described as a comparative study of the circumstances and consequences of different kinds of social action and research leading to social action (Acharya & Mohanty, 2019). On the other hand, the one-group pretest-posttest design is a research design where a single group of participants is observed twice: once before the intervention (pretest) and once after the intervention (posttest) (Cresswell, 2014). This design is used to assess the effects of an intervention or treatment by comparing outcomes before and after it is implemented, allowing researchers to infer changes that can be attributed to the intervention. However, it is important to note that this design lacks a control group, which can make it difficult to rule out other factors that might cause changes between the pretest and posttest (John Protzko et al., 2017).

This study will investigate the push-up performance of Grade 11 students before and after their exposure to Modern Arnis training. The entire Grade 11 students will serve as one single group in this study. All participants will undergo Modern Arnis training that will be handled by their respective teachers.

Participants

The participants of this study are Grade 11 students that are currently enrolled with PEH 102 – Modern Arnis. The age of the students ranges from 15-17 years of age, which made them a vulnerable population because they are still minors and needs their parent's/guardian's consent. As part of the ethical considerations, each learner was provided consent and assent forms in a form of a google form (see Appendix A). In order to participate, each learner should submit to their respective Physical Education teacher the signed parent's consent and assent forms. Instead of signature, the participants were requested to write their full name as their signature for the form. The teacher shall not allow the student to participate unless there is an authorization coming from the parent/guardian allowing their child, the student, to participate. Instead of signature, writing the full name of the parent/guardian served as legal authorization or signature for the form. Aside from the consent and assent forms, the students also submitted the pre-requisite files like their health declaration form (see Appendix B), comprised of their health appraisal record/medical record and physical activity readiness/level questionnaire. Without these pre-requisite files, the student shall not participate in the study.

The researchers have exposed the students to Modern Arnis that allowed the students to experience the basic and advanced skills. The researchers will utilize a simple random sampling procedure. Simple random sampling (SRS) is a fundamental statistical technique in which every individual in a population has an equal chance of being selected. This method is efficient for populations with similar characteristics and guarantees that each potential sample has an equal probability of being chosen, making it a fundamental aspect of impartial statistical inference (Latpate et al., 2021). In this study, since there will be 1000 Grade 11 students enrolled in the XUSHS, the researchers identified 285 samples for the data analysis. The 285 samples represented the four strands of senior high school, namely Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (n=145), Accountancy, Business and Management (n=42), Humanities and Social Sciences (n=70), and Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood (n=28) strands. The researchers have gathered first all the data of the 1000 participants. Each participant was assigned to a specific code. The researchers then conducted a simple random sampling through an application that generates random numbers.

The researchers practice maximum tolerance of ethical considerations. Participants have the right to reject the proposal of participating to the study. This decision will not affect their current academic status in PEH102. Furthermore, if the data collection process is ongoing and the participant decides to withdraw from the collection process, the researcher will wholeheartedly respect the decision of the decision of the participant and still will not affect the participant's academic status in the course.

Instrument

This study will adopt the push-up test of the Department of Education's Revised Physical Fitness Test (2019). The push-up test is a widely used fitness assessment tool designed to measure upper body muscular endurance (Riebe et al., 2018). It evaluates the strength and endurance of key muscles in the chest, shoulders, and triceps (Baechle & Earle, 2008). This test is often incorporated into physical fitness evaluations for various groups, including military personnel, sports teams, and general fitness enthusiasts, due to its straightforward nature and minimal equipment requirements (McArdle et al., 2010). During the test, participants perform as many push-ups as possible with correct form until they reach exhaustion. The total number of correctly executed push-ups is then recorded, providing valuable data to establish baseline fitness levels, track progress, and tailor exercise programs to individual needs (Riebe et al., 2018).

To conduct the push-up test, an exercise mat is required. The tester begins by lying face down in the standard push-up position, with palms on the mat shoulder-width apart, fingers pointing forward, and legs straight and slightly apart, supported by the toes. For boys, the arms are straightened while keeping the back and knees straight, lowering the body until the elbows form a 90-degree angle. For girls, the procedure is similar but with the knees in contact with the floor. Testers perform as many push-ups as possible at a cadence

of 20 per minute, with a maximum of 50 push-ups for boys and 25 for girls. A partner counts the repetitions, ensuring correct form and ending the test if the tester can no longer maintain proper form, experiences pain, voluntarily stops, or cannot keep the cadence. The final score is the total number of correctly performed push-ups (Revised Physical Fitness Test Manual, 2019).

Procedure

The research started with approval from the school principal through a formal letter that was endorsed by the Strand Head for HUMSS, School's Research Coordinator, and the Assistant Principal for Academics. After gaining approval, the teacher-researchers started to implement the study. The teacher-researchers provided the learners with consent and assent forms. In order to participate, the forms must be filled out and signed by the parents and the learners. Without the parent's/guardian's permission, the student will not be permitted to join the study.

During the second week of the semester, the pretest for the push-up test will be administered by the teacher-researchers. All the data gathered shall be recorded on the students' scoring cards. The scoring cards shall then be collected by the researchers to organize the data for the push-up performance pretest results.

On the third week of the semester, the teacher-researchers will start exposing the students to the basic and advanced skills in Modern Arnis. These include the warm-up activities of the students. This exposure to Modern Arnis skills will last until the 15th week of the semester. This will give the students at least 13 weeks of exposure to Modern Arnis training.

On the 16th week of the semester, the teacher-researchers will conduct the post-test of the push-up performance. On the same week, the teacher-researchers will gather all the scoring card to organize and analyze the push-up performance. This time, the teacher-researchers will compare the results of students' push-up performance before and after exposure to the 13-week Modern Arnis training. The data will be run through JASP application. The researchers will analyze and interpret the results afterwards.

The researchers practice maximum tolerance of ethical considerations. Participants have the right to reject the proposal of participating to the study. This decision will not affect their current academic status in PEH102. Furthermore, if the data collection process is ongoing and the participant decides to withdraw from the collection process, the researcher will wholeheartedly respect the decision of the decision of the participant and still will not affect the participant's academic status in the course.

In this research paper focused on enhancing learner experiences within physical education settings, we address potential health risks associated with physical activities, particularly heat exhaustion. To mitigate this risk, physical education and health (PEH) teachers will enforce a policy requiring students to bring water bottles to each session, which will be noted as part of their attendance record. Additionally, students are encouraged to bring extra shirts to manage perspiration effectively during physical activities. These measures are integral to ensuring hydration and comfort, thus reducing the likelihood of heat exhaustion.

Considering the scope of this study primarily involves exploring the experiences of learners rather than engaging them in strenuous physical activities, the risks anticipated are minimal. The research design emphasizes moderate physical engagement, focusing on the qualitative aspects of participation in physical education. This approach ensures that the physical demands do not exceed the capabilities of any participant, thereby maintaining a safe and inclusive environment for all involved.

The researcher will cover any costs that participants incur as part of their involvement in the study. This coverage may include expenditures for necessary equipment, transportation, and other relevant costs directly related to conducting the research. To ensure reimbursement, participants must receive prior approval for these expenses from the researcher before they undertake any out-of-pocket spending. This pre-approval process helps manage the study's budget effectively and ensures that all expenditures align with the study's financial guidelines.

Under the requirements of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal information collected from participants as part of this study will be kept confidential. Recorded materials such as video captures, photographs, and voice recordings of participants will solely be used for validation purposes within the context of the study. Furthermore, any documents shared by participants will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will not be disclosed without explicit written consent from the individuals involved.

The collected data will be securely stored within the Physical Education and Health (PEH) department's designated data storage facilities for a period of three years. After this retention period, the department will responsibly destroy all the collected data, including both printed materials and digital files. This ensures that participants' information is safeguarded throughout the duration of its use and properly disposed of, in compliance with privacy and data protection standards.

Data dissemination within the context of this study will be strictly limited to academic purposes, particularly for publication in scholarly journals. However, the raw data collected from participants, which may contain sensitive information, will not be disclosed publicly to safeguard participant privacy. Importantly, certain individuals within the academic community of Xavier University Senior High School (XUSHS)—including the principal, strand heads, academic departmental coordinators, and all faculty and staff—are not considered part of the general public. These individuals will not have access to the raw data unless it is essential for academic or administrative purposes and approved within the established privacy protocols. This selective accessibility ensures that all participant information remains confidential and is only used for its intended research purpose.

Participants in the study have the right to withdraw at any stage during the implementation or data collection phases. It is crucial that they feel comfortable and in control of their participation, which is entirely voluntary. They may discontinue their involvement at any time without any consequences. If participants decide to withdraw or if they have any questions or need further information about their participation, they are encouraged to contact the researcher directly at evargas@xu.edu.ph and mcatiil@xu.edu.ph. This provision ensures that all participants have ready access to support and assistance throughout the study process.

Data Analysis

This study collected two sets of data. First was the pretest push-up performance data and second was the post-test data. There were only two research questions that were answered, the first was about the performance of the participants during the pretest and post-test push-up performance, and if there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test result. The first question required descriptive statistics like the central tendencies, standard deviation and variance, and skewness of the data. The second question required inferential statistics like the paired samples T-test to determine the difference between pretest and post-test push-up performance after exposure to the Modern Arnis training.

Results and Discussion

What is the push-up performance of the participants before and after Modern Arnis training?

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the push-up performances of the participants before and after the 13-week Modern Arnis training exposure.

Table 1. *Pretest and Post Test Push-Up Performances of the Participants*

	<i>Push-Up Pretest</i>	<i>Push-Up Post-Test</i>
Valid	285	285
Missing	0	0
Mode	10.000 ^a	17.000 ^a
Median	10.000	16.000
Mean	11.754	16.730
Std. Deviation	8.931	10.844
Coefficient of variation	0.760	0.648
Skewness	1.162	1.254
Std. Error of Skewness	0.144	0.144
Kurtosis	1.732	3.336
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.288	0.288
Minimum	0.000	1.000
Maximum	49.000	75.000
Sum	3350.000	4768.000

^a The mode is computed assuming that variables are discreet

The descriptive statistics for the push-up performance of participants before and after Modern Arnis training show noticeable differences. In the pre-test, the mode was 10 push-ups, the median was 10 push-ups, and the mean was 11.754 push-ups. The standard deviation was 8.391, with a coefficient of variation of 0.760. The skewness of the pre-test data was 1.162, with a kurtosis of 1.732. The minimum number of push-ups recorded was 3, and the maximum was 49. The total sum of push-ups performed by all participants was 3,150.

In contrast, the post-test statistics show that the mode increased to 17 push-ups, the median to 16 push-ups, and the mean to 16.730 push-ups. The standard deviation also increased to 10.844, with a coefficient of variation of 0.648. The skewness of the post-test data was slightly higher at 1.254, and the kurtosis increased to 3.336. The minimum number of push-ups recorded decreased to 1, while the maximum number increased significantly to 75. The total sum of push-ups performed by all participants in the post-test was 4,768.

The push-up performance of participants showed marked improvement after undergoing Modern Arnis training. Descriptive statistics revealed significant increases in mode, median, and mean push-up counts, which indicate enhanced upper body muscular endurance. Specifically, the mode increased from 10 to 17 push-ups, the median from 10 to 16 push-ups, and the mean from 11.754 to 16.730 push-ups. The total sum of push-ups performed by participants also increased from 3,150 to 4,768. These improvements are consistent with findings from recent studies that highlight the benefits of martial arts training on physical fitness. For example, Baek et al. (2021) demonstrated that Taekwondo training significantly improves body composition and muscular endurance, supporting the observed enhancements in the current study.

Furthermore, the increase in variability, as shown by the standard deviation, from 8.391 to 10.844, and the expanded range of push-up counts suggest diverse individual responses to the training program. This aligns with the insights provided by DeBlauw et al. (2021), who emphasized the role of personalized training programs in maximizing fitness outcomes and reducing variability. Additionally, the positive skewness and increased kurtosis in the post-test results, indicating a more peaked distribution with some participants achieving

exceptionally high push-up counts, reflect the impact of high-intensity training components in Modern Arnis. High-intensity functional training (HIIFT) methods, as reviewed by Wang et al. (2023), have been shown to significantly enhance muscle strength and endurance, further validating the improvements noted in this study.

The observed improvements in push-up performance after Modern Arnis training might be influenced by several factors beyond the training itself. One such factor is the participants' engagement in other physical activities, such as household chores or current endeavors that could impact their muscular strength and endurance levels. Studies have shown that daily physical activities significantly contribute to overall fitness levels (Ibáñez et al., 2023). For instance, the physical demands of household chores can enhance muscular endurance, potentially affecting the results of fitness assessments (Cruz et al., 2022).

Another factor to consider is the possibility of dishonesty among participants. Despite reiterations from teacher-researchers that performance would not affect academic standings, some students might exaggerate their performance to boost their confidence. This issue is not uncommon in self-reported or self-monitored fitness assessments. Research indicates that self-efficacy and motivation can significantly influence how individuals report their physical activities and performance, sometimes leading to inaccuracies (Lithopoulos et al., 2020; Yu & Song, 2022). The potential for dishonesty in self-assessment highlights the importance of external verification in fitness testing to ensure accurate results (Pacholek, 2021).

Additionally, incorrect execution of the push-up test by participants could affect the results. Even with serious implementation by teacher-implementers, some students might not pay close attention to the instructions or might be distracted during the demonstration. This could lead to improper form, which compromises the validity of the test results. Studies emphasize the importance of proper technique in fitness assessments to obtain reliable data (Invernizzi et al., 2020). Misexecution of exercises can significantly skew the outcomes of fitness tests, highlighting the need for careful monitoring and guidance during the assessment process (Rodríguez-Rosell et al., 2020).

These factors suggest that while the Modern Arnis training appears effective, the results must be interpreted with caution, considering the possible external influences on participants' performance. Ensuring accurate and honest reporting, along with strict adherence to proper exercise techniques, is crucial for obtaining valid and reliable fitness assessment data (Alves et al., 2022).

Is there a significant difference between the participants' push-up performance before and after Modern Arnis training?

To determine if there is a significant difference between the participants' push-up performance before and after the 13-week Modern Arnis training exposure, a Paired Samples T-Test was conducted. The results are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2. Paired Samples T-Test of the Pretest and Post-test Results

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Cohen's d	SE Cohen's d	95% CI for Cohen's d	
									Lower	Upper
Pretest	- Post-Test	-14.281	284	<.001	-4.975	0.348	-0.846	0.039	-0.981	-0.710

Note. Student's t-test.

The results of the Paired Samples T-Test indicate a statistically significant improvement in push-up performance following the Modern Arnis training. Specifically, the t-value of -14.281 and the p-value of less than .001 highlight that the difference observed between the pretest and post-test performances is highly significant. The negative t-value suggests that the scores on the post-test were higher, which is corroborated by the mean difference of -4.975. This mean difference indicates that, on average, participants performed approximately 5 more push-ups in the post-test compared to the pretest.

The standard error of the mean difference, 0.348, suggests a relatively small variation around the mean difference, which contributes to the robustness of the statistical significance. Furthermore, Cohen's d of -0.846 denotes a large effect size, implying that the improvement in push-up performance is not only statistically significant but also practically meaningful. The confidence interval for Cohen's d (0.039, -0.981, -0.710) does not include zero, reinforcing the conclusion that the Modern Arnis training had a substantial impact on the participants' muscular endurance.

The significant improvement in push-up performance can be attributed to the high-intensity and comprehensive nature of the Modern Arnis training. This type of training likely involves a variety of exercises that target multiple muscle groups, thereby enhancing overall muscular endurance and strength. The large effect size observed in this study suggests that Modern Arnis, as a structured physical activity, can be a powerful tool for improving physical fitness parameters such as push-up performance.

A study by Fernández-Sanjurjo et al. (2020) supports these findings. Fernández-Sanjurjo et al. (2020) investigated the effects of high-intensity interval training (HIIT) on muscular fitness and found significant improvements in various measures of muscular endurance, including push-up performance, in a sample of adults. The current findings, indicating that structured, high-intensity training programs can effectively enhance physical fitness. This adds to the growing body of evidence that high-intensity training methods, like Modern Arnis, are beneficial for improving specific fitness outcomes.

The potential for dishonesty in self-assessment is a significant factor that can skew the outcomes of fitness tests like the push-up test. Despite clear instructions and reassurances from teacher-researchers that performance would not affect academic standings, some

students might exaggerate their performance to boost their confidence. This issue is not uncommon in self-reported or self-monitored fitness assessments. Research indicates that self-efficacy and motivation can significantly influence how individuals report their physical activities and performance, sometimes leading to inaccuracies (Kasović et al., 2020; Lithopoulos et al., 2020). This phenomenon can result in inflated results that do not accurately reflect the true physical capabilities of the participants, thereby compromising the validity of the test outcomes.

Dishonesty in self-reported fitness data is a well-documented issue. Studies have shown that individuals often misreport their physical fitness levels, either consciously or unconsciously. For instance, a study by Aandstad (2023) found significant discrepancies between self-reported and objectively measured physical fitness in young men and women. The study highlighted that more women than men tended to over-report their fitness levels (Aandstad, 2021). Such discrepancies can be attributed to a variety of factors, including social desirability bias, where individuals wish to present themselves in a more favorable light. This tendency can lead to overestimation of one's physical abilities, thereby affecting the reliability of fitness test results.

Mastery of the push-up test technique is another crucial factor that can impact the validity of the test results. Even with serious implementation by teacher-implementers, some students might not pay close attention to the instructions or might be distracted during the demonstration. This could lead to improper form, which compromises the validity of the test results. Proper technique is essential in fitness assessments to ensure that the data collected is accurate and reliable. Studies emphasize the importance of proper technique in fitness assessments to obtain reliable data. For example, a study by Rodríguez-Rosell et al. (2020) on the relationship between velocity loss and repetitions in reserve in the bench press and back squat exercises highlighted the importance of technique in ensuring accurate performance measurement (Rodríguez-Rosell et al., 2020).

The implication of improper technique is that it can lead to inconsistent and unreliable test results. Participants who have mastered the push-up test technique are likely to perform better and more consistently than those who have not. This mastery not only ensures that the muscles targeted by the test are properly engaged but also helps in maintaining a consistent standard across different testing sessions. Without proper technique, the results may reflect variability that is more related to differences in form rather than actual improvements in muscular strength or endurance. Therefore, it is critical for educators and trainers to ensure that participants understand and can correctly perform the exercises being tested.

In conclusion, the reliability of fitness test results like the push-up test can be significantly affected by factors such as dishonesty in self-assessment and improper execution of the test technique. Ensuring accurate self-reporting and proper technique are essential for obtaining valid and reliable data. Addressing these issues can lead to more accurate assessments of physical fitness and better-informed training and intervention programs.

Conclusions

The significant improvements in push-up performance observed after the Modern Arnis training suggest that incorporating high-intensity martial arts training into physical education programs can substantially enhance students' muscular endurance. This type of training provides a comprehensive workout that targets multiple muscle groups, making it a valuable addition to traditional fitness routines. Physical education instructors should consider integrating Modern Arnis or similar high-intensity training regimens to boost students' overall physical fitness effectively (Sanchez et al., 2020).

However, the potential for dishonesty in self-assessment needs to be addressed to ensure the accuracy of fitness test results. Teachers and trainers should implement strategies to mitigate the likelihood of exaggerated self-reporting. This could include using external verification methods such as video recordings of performances or employing objective measures like wearable fitness trackers. These tools can help ensure that the recorded data accurately reflects the participants' true abilities, thereby improving the reliability of the results (Kasović et al., 2020).

Additionally, proper technique execution is crucial for the validity of fitness assessments. Instructors should place a strong emphasis on teaching and reinforcing the correct form for exercises like push-ups. This can be achieved through detailed demonstrations, regular feedback, and corrective coaching. Ensuring that students understand and can perform exercises correctly will lead to more accurate and reliable assessment outcomes, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of physical education programs (Rodríguez-Rosell et al., 2020).

Future research should explore the long-term effects of Modern Arnis training on various aspects of physical fitness beyond muscular endurance. Studies could investigate its impact on cardiovascular health, flexibility, and body composition to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the benefits of this training modality. Additionally, research could examine the psychological effects of martial arts training, such as its influence on self-esteem, discipline, and stress management.

Further studies should also address the issue of self-assessment accuracy in fitness testing. Research could explore the effectiveness of different verification methods, such as video analysis and wearable technology, in improving the reliability of self-reported fitness data. Additionally, studies could investigate the psychological factors that contribute to dishonesty in self-assessments, providing insights into how these factors can be mitigated in educational and fitness settings.

The study findings underscore the significant positive impact of the 13-week Modern Arnis training on push-up performance, highlighting the potential of high-intensity martial arts training to enhance physical fitness. However, the accuracy of fitness assessments can be compromised by factors such as dishonesty in self-reporting and improper technique execution. Addressing these issues through external verification methods and rigorous instructional practices is essential to obtain valid and reliable fitness data.

Future research should continue to explore the broader benefits of Modern Arnis training and develop strategies to improve the accuracy of self-assessments in fitness testing. By doing so, educators and trainers can ensure that physical education programs are both effective and reliable, ultimately contributing to better health and fitness outcomes for participants.

In conclusion, while Modern Arnis training has proven effective in improving push-up performance, attention must be paid to the integrity of data collection methods and the quality of instruction. Ensuring accurate assessments and proper technique will maximize the benefits of such training programs and provide a solid foundation for further research and application in physical education and fitness contexts.

References

- Aandstad, A. (2021). Relationship between self-reported and objectively measured physical fitness in young men and women. *European Journal of Sport Science*, 23(2), 301–309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2021.2012597>
- Abu Talip, N. K., Bonnie, E., Ismail, Z., & Md Razali, M. R. (2021). COMPARISON OF LOW-LOAD BENCH PRESS AND PUSH-UP EXERCISES ON MUSCULAR PERFORMANCE AMONG FEMALE YOUTH. *Malaysian Journal of Movement, Health & Exercise*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.15282/mohe.v10i1.494>
- Acharya, A., & Mohanty, P. K. (2019). Action research. In *Qualitative techniques for workplace data analysis* (pp. 221–245). IGI Global.
- Alves, R. C., Enes, A., Follador, L., Prestes, J., & da Silva, S. G. (2022). Effect of Different Training Programs at Self-Selected Intensity on Body Composition, Perceptual Responses and Fitness Outcomes in Obese Women. *International Journal of Exercise Science*, 15(4), 373.
- Amara, S., Chortane, O. G., Negra, Y., Hammami, R., Khalifa, R., Chortane, S. G., & van den Tillaar, R. (2021). Relationship between Swimming Performance, Biomechanical Variables and the Calculated Predicted 1-RM Push-up in Competitive Swimmers. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(21), 11395. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182111395>
- Artanayasa, I. W., Kusuma, K. C. A., & Ariawan, K. U. (2023). Push-Up Counter (PUC) as an instrument of arm muscle strength: Validity and reliability. *Journal Sport Area*, 8(3), 350–359. [https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2023.vol8\(3\).13245](https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2023.vol8(3).13245)
- Azeez, S. R., & Majeed, W. K. (2022). Muscular strength training and its effect on strength endurance and speed in wheelchair tennis players. *SPORT TK-Revista EuroAmericana de Ciencias Del Deporte*, 53. <https://doi.org/10.6018/sportk.526731>
- Baechle, T. R., & Earle, R. W. (2008). *Essentials of strength training and conditioning*. Human kinetics.
- Baek, S., Park, J.-B., Choi, S.-H., Lee, J.-D., & Nam, S.-S. (2021). Effects of Taekwondo Training on Body Composition: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(21), 11550. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182111550>
- Bull, F. C., Al-Ansari, S. S., Biddle, S., Borodulin, K., Buman, M. P., Cardon, G., Carty, C., Chaput, J.-P., Chastin, S., Chou, R., Dempsey, P. C., DiPietro, L., Ekelund, U., Firth, J., Friedenreich, C. M., Garcia, L., Gichu, M., Jago, R., Katzmarzyk, P. T., ... Willumsen, J. F. (2020). World Health Organization 2020 guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 54(24), 1451–1462. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2020-102955>
- Cresswell, J. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (Fourth Ed.).
- Cruz, A. B., Cando, J. M., & Kim, H.-D. (2022). Physical activity, sedentary behavior, and health states of university students during the first wave of COVID-19 community quarantine in the Philippines. *Frontiers in Education*, 7.
- DeBlauw, J. A., Drake, N. B., Kurtz, B. K., Crawford, D. A., Carper, M. J., Wakeman, A., & Heinrich, K. M. (2021). High-Intensity Functional Training Guided by Individualized Heart Rate Variability Results in Similar Health and Fitness Improvements as Predetermined Training with Less Effort. *Journal of Functional Morphology and Kinesiology*, 6(4), 102. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jfkm6040102>
- Dhar, D. K., & Purwar, B. (2023). Effect of Body Fat and BMI on Muscle Strength and Endurance in Young Adults: A Cross-sectional Study. *JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC RESEARCH*. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2023/63970.18568>
- Endab, J. P., Mondelo, R. B., & Vargas, E. (2024). International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews Basic Alternatives in Developing Needed Endurance (B . A . D . N . E) to Improve High School Student ' s Push -up Performance in Fitness Gram Test. 5, 3345–3349.

Fernández-Sanjurjo, M., Úbeda, N., Fernández-García, B., del Valle, M., Ramírez de Molina, A., Crespo, M. C., Martín-Hernández, R., Casas-Agustench, P., Martínez-Cambor, P., de Gonzalo-Calvo, D., Díez-Robles, S., García-González, Á., Montero, A., González-González, F., Rabadán, M., Díaz-Martínez, Á. E., Whitham, M., Iglesias-Gutiérrez, E., & Dávalos, A. (2020). Exercise dose affects the circulating microRNA profile in response to acute endurance exercise in male amateur runners. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 30(10), 1896–1907. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13759>

Fredrick, R. N., & Silverman, S. (2020). Relationship between Urban Middle School Physical Education Teachers' Attitudes toward Fitness Testing and Student Performance on Fitness Tests. *Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science*, 24(4), 273–281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1091367X.2020.1815024>

Goud, K., Basireddy, A., J. G., & A, C. (2023). A comparative study of muscle strength and muscle endurance in strength trained and untrained human beings. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 13(8), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5455/njppp.2023.13.09445202204012022>

Ibáñez, S. J., Piñar, M. I., García, D., & Mancha-Triguero, D. (2023). Physical Fitness as a Predictor of Performance during Competition in Professional Women's Basketball Players. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(2), 988. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20020988>

Invernizzi, P. L., Signorini, G., Bosio, A., Raiola, G., & Scurati, R. (2020). Validity and Reliability of Self-Perception-Based Submaximal Fitness Tests in Young Adult Females: An Educational Perspective. *Sustainability*, 12(6), 2265. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12062265>

John Protzko, Nijenhuis, J. te, Ziada, K. E., Metwaly, H. A. M., & Bakhiet, S. F. (2017). What to do Without a Control Group: You have to go latent, but not all latents are equa. *Вестник Росздравнадзора*, 4(1), 9–15.

Kasović, M., Štefan, L., & Zvonar, M. (2020). Self-Reported vs Measured Physical Fitness in Older Women. *Clinical Interventions in Aging*, Volume 15, 425–430. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CIA.S240156>

Latpate, R., Kshirsagar, J., Kumar Gupta, V., & Chandra, G. (2021). Simple Random Sampling. In *Advanced Sampling Methods* (pp. 11–35). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-0622-9_2

Lipardo, D., Manlapaz, D., Orpilla, V., Arevalo, J. T., Buan, J. C., Cortez, J. L., Desquitado, K. P., Geli, V. M., Lacorte, J. R., Masibay, J., Sanchez, C. J., & Villanueva, A. D. (2022). Arnis-based Exercise Program for Balance Control in Community-Dwelling Older Adults: Study Protocol for a Pilot Randomized Controlled Trial. *Philippine Journal of Physical Therapy*, 1(3), 3–12. <https://doi.org/10.46409/002.JEQ6438>

Lithopoulos, A., Grant, S. J., Williams, D. M., & Rhodes, R. E. (2020). Experimental comparison of physical activity self-efficacy measurement: Do vignettes reduce motivational confounding? *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 47, 101642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2019.101642>

Marquina Nieto, M., Rivilla-García, J., de la Rubia, A., & Lorenzo-Calvo, J. (2022). Assessment of the Speed and Power of Push-Ups Performed on Surfaces with Different Degrees of Instability. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(21), 13739. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192113739>

McArdle, W. D., Katch, F. I., & Katch, V. L. (2010). *Exercise physiology: nutrition, energy, and human performance*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

Nazilah, N., Aryanti, S., & Victorian, A. R. (2023). Push Up Exercise Against 50 Meter Swimming Speed Breaststroke. *Kinestetik : Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Jasmani*, 7(3), 660–672. <https://doi.org/10.33369/jk.v7i3.29979>

Pacholek, M. (2021). The Effects of Various Stimuli on Motivation and Physical Fitness of Physically Active and Non-Active Students. *Annals of Applied Sport Science*, 9(4), 0–0. <https://doi.org/10.52547/aassjournal.954>

Revised Physical Fitness Test Manual, (2019). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/12/09/december-9-2019-do-034-s-2019-revised-physical-fitness-test-manual/>

Riebe, D., Ehrman, J. K., Liguori, G., & Magal, M. (2018). *ACSM's guidelines for exercise testing and prescription*. Wolters Kluwer.

Rodríguez-Rosell, D., Yáñez-García, J. M., Sánchez-Medina, L., Mora-Custodio, R., & González-Badillo, J. J. (2020). Relationship Between Velocity Loss and Repetitions in Reserve in the Bench Press and Back Squat Exercises. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 34(9), 2537–2547. <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000002881>

Rozenek, R., Byrne, J. J., Crussemeyer, J., & Garhammer, J. (2022). Male-Female Differences in Push-up Test Performance at Various Cadences. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 36(12), 3324–3329. <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000004091>

Sanchez, D. T., Peconcillo, L. B., Wong, R. L., Panzo, R. C., Flores, M. C. A., Labrado, O. A., & Godinez, J. A. T. (2020). Exploring The Lived Experiences Of Young Arnisadors: The Curricular and Co-Curricular Challenges. *Solid State Technology*, 63(4).

<https://doi.org/10.35877/jsst.v63.i2s.4114>

Subrata, T., Ni Wayan Rusni, & I Nyoman Arie Purwana. (2022). Comparison of Push-Up Exercise Methods on Push-Up Test Ability in Medical Students at Warmadewa University. *WMJ (Warmadewa Medical Journal)*, 7(1), 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.22225/wmj.7.1.4605.40-46>

Wang, X., Soh, K. G., Samsudin, S., Deng, N., Liu, X., Zhao, Y., & Akbar, S. (2023). Effects of high-intensity functional training on physical fitness and sport-specific performance among the athletes: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *PLOS ONE*, 18(12), e0295531. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0295531>

Ward, P., Chey, W. S., & Cho, K. (2023). Evaluating the Content Knowledge of Preservice Physical Education Teachers. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 42(2), 293–300. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.2021-0291>

Xu, G. (2023). Effectiveness of English as A Medium of Instruction in Physical Education. *Journal of Education and Educational Research*, 3(2), 205–210. <https://doi.org/10.54097/jeer.v3i2.9305>

Yu, G., & Song, Y. (2022). What affects sports participation and life satisfaction among urban residents? The role of self-efficacy and motivation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 884953.

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